

Detection of spikes in the Tycho data streams

L. Lindegren
Lund Observatory

Introduction

Elementary statistical methods are applied in this note to the problem of detecting spikes in the Tycho data streams. A spike is an isolated sample with much higher count than expected from surrounding samples. (Sometimes, however, two adjacent samples may be affected.) The detection criteria discussed here take advantage of the fact that a spike is generally much narrower than the bump caused by the transit of a star across a starmapper slit. (The latter has a full width at half maximum of at least 3 samples.) More sophisticated criteria could make use of the characteristic signature of a group transit to distinguish stars from spikes, but this is not considered here.

The successive steps required for defining a suitable detection/elimination strategy are roughly as follows:

- (1) formulate a null hypothesis ('no spike') and estimate the parameter(s) of the corresponding count model;
- (2) define a goodness-of-fit measure (t) and derive its distribution under the null hypothesis;
- (3) select a threshold value T such that the null hypothesis is rejected if $t > T$. The threshold is chosen to give an acceptably low rate of false detections;
- (4) derive the power of the resulting criterion, i.e., its capability to detect spikes of different amplitudes and shapes;
- (5) derive the criterion's sensitivity to star transits and, if necessary, find a procedure for recognising such cases of mistaken detections;
- (6) combine the above findings into a practical algorithm, including some method to remove detected spikes;
- (7) test the algorithm on simulated and real data and modify for optimum performance.

This note covers mainly steps 1–5 for two very simple detection criteria called A and B.

Criterion A

Let $\dots, n_{k-2}, n_{k-1}, n_k, n_{k+1}, n_{k+2}, \dots$ be a sequence of photon counts (samples) from one of the Tycho data streams (B_T or V_T), with a possible spike in the k th sample. We wish to formulate a criterion for determining whether n_k is really a spike, or just a normal fluctuation of the counts, or perhaps part of a star transit.

Let us disregard for the moment the presence of transits and assume that the samples — apart from the spikes— are simply independent realisations of a Poisson process with constant (but unknown) mean value b . To test whether n_k is a spike we may consider the three samples $k-1, k, k+1$ and formulate the null hypothesis as follows: n_{k-1}, n_k, n_{k+1} are Poisson variables with the same mean value b . To simplify notations let us denote the counts x, y, z instead of

n_{k-1}, n_k, n_{k+1} . Under the null hypothesis, the maximum likelihood estimate of b is obtained by maximising

$$L(b) = \left(\frac{b^x}{x!} e^{-b}\right) \left(\frac{b^y}{y!} e^{-b}\right) \left(\frac{b^z}{z!} e^{-b}\right) \quad [1]$$

yielding, of course,

$$\hat{b} = \frac{x + y + z}{3} \quad [2]$$

As a measure of the goodness-of-fit we use the chi-square statistic

$$t_A = \frac{(x - \hat{b})^2 + (y - \hat{b})^2 + (z - \hat{b})^2}{\hat{b}} \quad [3a]$$

$$= 3 \frac{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}{x + y + z} - (x + y + z) \quad [3b]$$

If there is no spike, then t_A will approximately follow the χ^2 distribution with 2 degrees of freedom, i.e.,

$$\Pr[t_A > \chi^2] = e^{-\chi^2/2} \quad [4]$$

Figure 1 shows that the actual distribution of t_A , obtained from numerical simulations of Poisson counts, is indeed very close to the theoretical exponential distribution, at least for $b > 5$.

We now proceed by choosing a threshold value T such that the null hypothesis is rejected if $t_A > T$. The threshold should be sufficiently low to 'catch' all significant spikes, yet high enough not to cause too many false detection. In practice the latter condition will usually set the threshold. E.g., if we can tolerate at most 1 false alarm per 10,000 background samples, we must choose $T \geq 2 \log 10^4 \simeq 18.42$.

Having chosen a threshold value we may ask how small spikes are likely to be detected with this criterion. The answer depends on the distribution of t_A under the alternative hypothesis, e.g., that x and z are Poissonian with mean value b , while y is the sum of a Poisson count with mean value b and a positive number s , equal to the amplitude of the spike. The exact distribution of t_A is not very important, but the expected value gives a useful estimate of the detection power as function of T and b : a spike of amplitude s will have about 50% chance of being detected if $E(t_A) = T$. (This assertion is based on the assumption that the distribution is not very skew, so that the mean and median are not very different.) By asymptotic expansion we find the approximate expression:

$$E(t_A) = \frac{6b + 2s^2}{3b + s} \quad [5]$$

The minimum detectable spike amplitude is then

$$s_{\min} = \frac{T}{4} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{T}{4}\right)^2 + \frac{3}{2}(T-2)b} \quad [6]$$

Note that the actual count in the spiked sample is the spike amplitude *plus* the background. With $T = 18.42$ and $b = 5, 15, 100$, for instance, we find $s_{\min} \simeq 17, 25, 55$, or $b + s_{\min} = 22, 40, 155$.

If spikes of amplitude $s_{\min}$ trigger the transit detection, then it will be necessary to lower the threshold T at the expense of more false spike detections.

Let us briefly consider also spikes affecting two consecutive samples (say, y and z). Assuming a constant background b and the spike amplitudes s_1 (on y) and s_2 (on z) we find

$$E(t_A) = \frac{6b + 2(s_1^2 + s_2^2 - s_1s_2)}{3b + s_1 + s_2} \quad [7]$$

The worst situation occurs when $s_1 = s_2 (= s, \text{ say})$, in which case the minimum detectable amplitude is reduced to

$$s'_{\min} = \frac{T}{2} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{T}{2}\right)^2 + \frac{3}{2}(T-2)b} \quad [8]$$

or $s'_{\min} = 24, 31, 60$ for $b = 5, 15, 100$.

We now come to the interesting question what happens when this criterion is applied to samples containing an actual star transit. Let a be the intensity of the star, in a unit such that the transit can be described as a Poisson process with count expectation

$$E(n_i) = b + aS(i - \tau) \quad [9]$$

τ is the transit time expressed in units of the sample time (1/600 s) and S is the normalised single-slit response function ($S(0) = 1$). Let $S_{-1} = S(k - 1 - \tau)$, $S_0 = S(k - \tau)$ and $S_1 = S(k + 1 - \tau)$ be the values of the SSR for the three samples x, y, z . Using similar expansions as before we find

$$E(t_A) = 2 + a \frac{S_{-1}^2 + S_0^2 + S_1^2 - S_{-1}S_0 - S_{-1}S_1 - S_0S_1}{(S_{-1} + S_0 + S_1) + (3b/a)} \quad [10]$$

Neglecting the term $(3b/a)$ we can write $E(t_A) = 2 + a f_A(\delta)$ where $\delta = k - \tau$ is the offset of the k th sample from the actual transit time. The spike detection criterion is likely to be triggered by a slit transit with amplitude greater than $a_{\text{lim}} = (T - 2)/f_{A\text{max}}$.

Figure 2 shows the function $f_A(\delta)$ computed from the provisional SSR calibration reported by H. Schrijver on 9-Jan-90 (ESTEC.STATUS.06). The solid curve is for the vertical slits (in B_T , SM #2, positive H), while the dashed curve is for the inclined slits. The function reaches a maximum of about 0.8 approximately 2 samples after (before?) a transit on the vertical slit. With $T = 18.42$ this corresponds to $a_{\text{lim}} \simeq 20$ or $B_T \simeq 8.5$.

The high sensitivity of this criterion to star transits is clearly a severe drawback since a large number of false detections must then be eliminated by some other, more elaborate process. We now proceed to examine a slightly different criterion, which should be less sensitive to transits.

Criterion B

It is seen from Figure 2 that the maximum response of t_A corresponds to the steepest parts of the SSR function. Thus a natural modification would be to permit a sloping background. Accordingly we formulate the null hypothesis as follows: x, y, z are Poisson variables with mean values $b - c$, b , and $b + c$, respectively, where b and c are parameters ($b > 0$, $|c| \leq b$). Under the null hypothesis, the maximum likelihood estimates of b and c are obtained by maximising

$$L(b, c) = \left(\frac{(b - c)^x}{x!} e^{-b+c} \right) \left(\frac{b^y}{y!} e^{-b} \right) \left(\frac{(b + c)^z}{z!} e^{-b+c} \right) \quad [11]$$

The likelihood equations $\partial \ln L / \partial b = 0$, $\partial \ln L / \partial c = 0$ are easily solved to give

$$\hat{b} = \frac{x + y + z}{3}, \quad \hat{c} = \frac{z - x}{z + x} \hat{b} \quad [12]$$

and the chi-square goodness-of-fit is obtained as

$$t_B = \frac{(x - \hat{b} + \hat{c})^2}{\hat{b} - \hat{c}} + \frac{(y - \hat{b})^2}{\hat{b}} + \frac{(x - \hat{b} - \hat{c})^2}{\hat{b} + \hat{c}} \quad [13b]$$

$$= 3 \frac{\frac{1}{2}(x + z)^2 + y^2}{x + y + z} - (x + y + z) \quad [13b]$$

If there is no spike, then t_B will approximately follow the χ^2 distribution with 1 degree of freedom, i.e.,

$$\Pr[t_B > \chi^2] = 2Q(\sqrt{\chi^2}) \quad [14]$$

($Q(u)$ denotes the complement of the cumulative normal distribution function, $Q(u) = (2\pi)^{-1/2} \int_u^\infty \exp(-\frac{1}{2}v^2) dv$.)

Figure 3 shows that the actual distribution, obtained by simulation, is very close to the theoretical even for small count rates.

As for criterion A we adopt a level of significance corresponding to 1 false detection per 10,000 background samples, i.e., $2Q(\sqrt{T}) = 10^{-4}$. This gives the threshold value $T = 15.14$.

The detection power of the resulting criterion is estimated in the same manner as for Criterion A, using the approximate result

$$E(t_B) = \frac{3b + 2s^2}{3b + s} \quad [15]$$

The minimum detectable spike amplitude is then

$$s_{\min} = \frac{T}{4} + \sqrt{\left(\frac{T}{4}\right)^2 + \frac{3}{2}(T - 1)b} \quad [16]$$

or $s_{\min} = 15, 22, 50$ for $b = 5, 15, 100$.

The response of Criterion B to a star transit can be estimated by means of the approximate expectation

$$E(t_A) = 1 + \frac{S_0 - \frac{1}{2}(S_{-1} + S_1)}{(S_{-1} + S_0 + S_1) + (3b/a)} + a \frac{[S_0 - \frac{1}{2}(S_{-1} + S_1)]^2}{(S_{-1} + S_0 + S_1) + (3b/a)} \quad [17a]$$

$$\simeq 1 + a f_B(\delta) \quad [17b]$$

where, as before, $\delta = k - \tau$ is the distance from the transit expressed in samples. Spike detection is likely to be triggered by stars with amplitude greater than $a_{\text{lim}} = (T - 1)/f_{B\text{max}}$.

Figure 4 shows the function $f_B(\delta)$ for the vertical and inclined slits according to ESTEC.STATUS.06 (B_T , SM # 2, positive H). The maximum is $\simeq 0.03$ at the points of maximum (negative) curvature of the SSR function; this gives $a_{r\text{mlim}} \simeq 470$ counts per sample, corresponding to $B_T \simeq 5.1$. Criterion B is thus about 25 times less sensitive than A to star transits, while its power to detect spikes is in fact slightly better (at the same level of significance).

Conclusions

Among simple (3-point) detection algorithms, Criterion B is probably a good choice: at an error rate of 10^{-4} (1 false detection per 10,000 true background samples) it will detect most spikes with an amplitude above some 15–25 counts, while being relatively insensitive to star transits. Moreover, the criterion requires no separate estimation of the local or global background level and the test statistic (t_B) can be computed in only nine arithmetic operations (no square root). The threshold is fixed, independent of the background, and determined only by the required level of significance. Finally, the general properties of the test statistic under different hypotheses can be assessed by simple analytical means.

Figure 1. Cumulative distribution functions for the statistic t_A obtained from numerical simulations of 100,000 samples with constant intensity equal to $b = 5, 15$ and 100 counts/sample.

Figure 2 (top): Sensitivity of t_A to a star transit

Figure 3 (bottom): Sensitivity of t_B to a star transit

Figure 3. Same as Figure 1 but for the statistic t_B .